

On Algebraic Multi-Ring Spaces

Linfan Mao

(Academy of Mathematics and System Sciences, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100080)

Abstract: A Smarandache multi-space is a union of n spaces A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n with some additional conditions holding. Combining Smarandache multi-spaces with rings in classical ring theory, the conception of multi-ring spaces is introduced. Some characteristics of a multi-ring space are obtained in this paper

Key words: ring, multi-space, multi-ring space, ideal subspace chain.

Classification: AMS(2000) 16U80, 16W25

1. Introduction

The notion of multi-spaces is introduced by Smarandache in [6] under his idea of hybrid mathematics: *combining different fields into a unifying field*([7]), which is defined as follows.

Definition 1.1 For any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ let A_i be a set with ensemble of law L_i , and the intersection of k sets $A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}, \dots, A_{i_k}$ of them constrains the law $I(A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}, \dots, A_{i_k})$. Then the union of $A_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$

$$\tilde{A} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n A_i$$

is called a *multi-space*.

As we known, a set R with two binary operation $+$ and \circ , denoted by $(R; +, \circ)$, is said to be a *ring* if for $\forall x, y \in R, x + y \in R, x \circ y \in R$, the following conditions hold.

- (i) $(R; +)$ is an abelian group;
- (ii) $(R; \circ)$ is a semigroup;
- (iii) For $\forall x, y, z \in R, x \circ (y + z) = x \circ y + x \circ z$ and $(x + y) \circ z = x \circ z + y \circ z$.

By combining Smarandache multi-spaces with rings, a new kind of algebraic structure called multi-ring space is found, which is defined in the following.

Definition 1.2 Let $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$ be a complete multi-space with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R}) = \{(+_i, \times_i), 1 \leq i \leq m\}$. If for any integers $i, j, i \neq j, 1 \leq i, j \leq m$, $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ is a ring and for $\forall x, y, z \in \tilde{R}$,

$$(x +_i y) +_j z = x +_i (y +_j z), \quad (x \times_i y) \times_j z = x \times_i (y \times_j z)$$

and

$$x \times_i (y +_j z) = x \times_i y +_j x \times_i z, \quad (y +_j z) \times_i x = y \times_i x +_j z \times_i x$$

if all their operation results exist, then \tilde{R} is called a multi-ring space. If for any integer $1 \leq i \leq m$, $(R; +_i, \times_i)$ is a filed, then \tilde{R} is called a multi-filed space.

For a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, let $\tilde{S} \subset \tilde{R}$ and $O(\tilde{S}) \subset O(\tilde{R})$, if \tilde{S} is also a multi-ring space with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{S})$, then call \tilde{S} a multi-ring subspace of \tilde{R} . We have the following criterions for the multi-ring subspaces.

The subject of this paper is to find some characteristics of a multi-ring space. For terminology and notation not defined here can be seen in [1], [5], [12] for algebraic terminologies and in [2], [6] – [11] for multi-spaces and logics.

2. Characteristics of a multi-ring space

First, we have the following result for multi-ring subspace of a multi-ring space.

Theorem 2.1 For a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, a subset $\tilde{S} \subset \tilde{R}$ with $O(\tilde{S}) \subset O(\tilde{R})$ is a multi-ring subspace of \tilde{R} if and only if for any integer $k, 1 \leq k \leq m$, $(\tilde{S} \cap R_k; +_k, \times_k)$ is a subring of $(R_k; +_k, \times_k)$ or $\tilde{S} \cap R_k = \emptyset$.

Proof For any integer $k, 1 \leq k \leq m$, if $(\tilde{S} \cap R_k; +_k, \times_k)$ is a subring of $(R_k; +_k, \times_k)$ or $\tilde{S} \cap R_k = \emptyset$, then since $\tilde{S} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (\tilde{S} \cap R_i)$, we know that \tilde{S} is a multi-ring subspace by definition of a multi-ring space.

Now if $\tilde{S} = \bigcup_{j=1}^s S_j$ is a multi-ring subspace of \tilde{R} with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{S}) = \{(+_{i_j}, \times_{i_j}), 1 \leq j \leq s\}$, then $(S_j; +_{i_j}, \times_{i_j})$ is a subring of $(R_{i_j}; +_{i_j}, \times_{i_j})$. Therefore, for any integer $j, 1 \leq j \leq s$, $S_j = R_{i_j} \cap \tilde{S}$. But for other integer $l \in \{i; 1 \leq i \leq m\} \setminus \{i_j; 1 \leq j \leq s\}$, $\tilde{S} \cap S_l = \emptyset$. \spadesuit

Applying the criterions for subrings of a ring, we get the following result.

Theorem 2.2 For a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, a subset $\tilde{S} \subset \tilde{R}$ with $O(\tilde{S}) \subset O(\tilde{R})$ is a multi-ring subspace of \tilde{R} if and only if for any double binary operations $(+_j, \times_j) \in O(\tilde{S})$, $(\tilde{S} \cap R_j; +_j) \prec (R_j; +_j)$ and $(\tilde{S}; \times_j)$ is complete.

Proof According to Theorem 2.1, we know that \tilde{S} is a multi-ring subspace if and only if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, $(\tilde{S} \cap R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ is a subring of $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ or $\tilde{S} \cap R_i = \emptyset$. By a well known criterions for subrings of a ring (see also [5]), we know

that $(\tilde{S} \cap R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ is a subring of $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ if and only if for any double binary operations $(+_j, \times_j) \in O(\tilde{S})$, $(\tilde{S} \cap R_j; +_j) \prec (R_j; +_j)$ and $(\tilde{S}; \times_j)$ is a complete set. This completes the proof. \spadesuit

We use the *ideal subspace chain* of a multi-ring space to characterize its structure properties. An *ideal subspace* \tilde{I} of a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$ with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R})$ is a multi-ring subspace of \tilde{R} satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) \tilde{I} is a multi-group subspace with operation set $\{+ | (+, \times) \in O(\tilde{I})\}$;
- (ii) for any $r \in \tilde{R}, a \in \tilde{I}$ and $(+, \times) \in O(\tilde{I})$, $r \times a \in \tilde{I}$ and $a \times r \in \tilde{I}$ if their operation results exist.

Theorem 2.3 *A subset \tilde{I} with $O(\tilde{I}), O(\tilde{I}) \subset O(\tilde{R})$ of a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$ with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R}) = \{(+_i, \times_i) | 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ is an ideal subspace if and only if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, $(\tilde{I} \cap R_i, +_i, \times_i)$ is an ideal of the ring $(R_i, +_i, \times_i)$ or $\tilde{I} \cap R_i = \emptyset$.*

Proof By definition of an ideal subspace, the necessity of the condition is obvious.

For the sufficiency, denote by $\tilde{R}(+, \times)$ the set of elements in \tilde{R} with binary operations $+$ and \times . If there exists an integer i such that $\tilde{I} \cap R_i \neq \emptyset$ and $(\tilde{I} \cap R_i, +_i, \times_i)$ is an ideal of $(R_i, +_i, \times_i)$, then for $\forall a \in \tilde{I} \cap R_i, \forall r_i \in R_i$, we know that

$$r_i \times_i a \in \tilde{I} \cap R_i; \quad a \times_i r_i \in \tilde{I} \cap R_i.$$

Notice that $\tilde{R}(+_i, \times_i) = R_i$. Therefore, we get that for $\forall r \in \tilde{R}$,

$$r \times_i a \in \tilde{I} \cap R_i; \quad \text{and} \quad a \times_i r \in \tilde{I} \cap R_i,$$

if their operation result exist. Whence, \tilde{I} is an ideal subspace of \tilde{R} . \spadesuit

An ideal subspace \tilde{I} of a multi-ring space \tilde{R} is said *maximal* if for any ideal subspace \tilde{I}' , if $\tilde{R} \supseteq \tilde{I}' \supseteq \tilde{I}$, then $\tilde{I}' = \tilde{R}$ or $\tilde{I}' = \tilde{I}$. For any order of the double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R})$ of a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, not loss of generality, assume it being $(+_1, \times_1) \succ (+_2, \times_2) \succ \cdots \succ (+_m, \times_m)$, we can define an *ideal subspace chain* of \tilde{R} by the following programming.

- (i) Construct the ideal subspace chain

$$\tilde{R} \supset \tilde{R}_{11} \supset \tilde{R}_{12} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{1s_1}$$

under the double binary operation $(+_1, \times_1)$, where \tilde{R}_{11} is a maximal ideal subspace of \tilde{R} and in general, for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m-1$, $\tilde{R}_{1(i+1)}$ is a maximal ideal subspace of \tilde{R}_{1i} .

- (ii) If the ideal subspace

$$\tilde{R} \supset \tilde{R}_{11} \supset \tilde{R}_{12} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{1s_1} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{i1} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{is_i}$$

has been constructed for $(+_1, \times_1) \succ (+_2, \times_2) \succ \cdots \succ (+_i, \times_i)$, $1 \leq i \leq m-1$, then construct an ideal subspace chain of \tilde{R}_{is_i}

$$\tilde{R}_{is_i} \supset \tilde{R}_{(i+1)1} \supset \tilde{R}_{(i+1)2} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{(i+1)s_i}$$

under the operations $(+_{i+1}, \times_{i+1})$, where $\tilde{R}_{(i+1)1}$ is a maximal ideal subspace of \tilde{R}_{is_i} and in general, $\tilde{R}_{(i+1)(i+1)}$ is a maximal ideal subspace of $\tilde{R}_{(i+1)j}$ for any integer $j, 1 \leq j \leq s_i - 1$. Define the ideal subspace chain of \tilde{R} under $(+_1, \times_1) \succ (+_2, \times_2) \succ \cdots \succ (+_{i+1}, \times_{i+1})$ being

$$\tilde{R} \supset \tilde{R}_{11} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{1s_1} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{i1} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{is_i} \supset \tilde{R}_{(i+1)1} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{(i+1)s_{i+1}}.$$

Similar to a multi-group space([3]), we have the following results for the ideal subspace chain of a multi-ring space.

Theorem 2.4 For a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, its ideal subspace chain only has finite terms if and only if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, the ideal chain of the ring $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ has finite terms, i.e., each ring $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ is an Artin ring.

Proof Let the order of double operations in $\vec{O}(\tilde{R})$ be

$$(+_1, \times_1) \succ (+_2, \times_2) \succ \cdots \succ (+_m, \times_m)$$

and a maximal ideal chain in the ring $(R_1; +_1, \times_1)$ is

$$R_1 \succ R_{11} \succ \cdots \succ R_{1t_1}.$$

Calculate

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}_{11} &= \tilde{R} \setminus \{R_1 \setminus R_{11}\} = R_{11} \bigcup \left(\bigcup_{i=2}^m R_i \right), \\ \tilde{R}_{12} &= \tilde{R}_{11} \setminus \{R_{11} \setminus R_{12}\} = R_{12} \bigcup \left(\bigcup_{i=2}^m R_i \right), \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{R}_{1t_1} = \tilde{R}_{1t_1} \setminus \{R_{1(t_1-1)} \setminus R_{1t_1}\} = R_{1t_1} \bigcup \left(\bigcup_{i=2}^m R_i \right).$$

According to Theorem 3.10, we know that

$$\tilde{R} \supset \tilde{R}_{11} \supset \tilde{R}_{12} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{1t_1}$$

is a maximal ideal subspace chain of \tilde{R} under the double binary operation $(+_1, \times_1)$. In general, for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m-1$, assume

$$R_i \succ R_{i1} \succ \cdots \succ R_{it_i}$$

is a maximal ideal chain in the ring $(R_{(i-1)t_{i-1}}; +_i, \times_i)$. Calculate

$$\tilde{R}_{ik} = R_{ik} \bigcup \left(\bigcup_{j=i+1}^m \right) \tilde{R}_{ik} \cap R_i$$

Then we know that

$$\tilde{R}_{(i-1)t_{i-1}} \supset \tilde{R}_{i1} \supset \tilde{R}_{i2} \supset \cdots \supset \tilde{R}_{it_i}$$

is a maximal ideal subspace chain of $\tilde{R}_{(i-1)t_{i-1}}$ under the double operation $(+_i, \times_i)$ by Theorem 3.10. Whence, if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, the ideal chain of the ring $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ has finite terms, then the ideal subspace chain of the multi-ring space \tilde{R} only has finite terms and if there exists one integer i_0 such that the ideal chain of the ring $(R_{i_0}, +_{i_0}, \times_{i_0})$ has infinite terms, then there must be infinite terms in the ideal subspace chain of the multi-ring space \tilde{R} . \spadesuit .

A multi-ring space is called an *Artin multi-ring space* if each ideal subspace chain only has finite terms. We have the following corollary by Theorem 3.11.

Corollary 2.1 *A multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m$ with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R}) = \{(+_i, \times_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ is an Artin multi-ring space if and only if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, the ring $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ is an Artin ring.*

For a multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m$ with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R}) = \{(+_i, \times_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq m\}$, an element e is an *idempotent* element if $e_{\times}^2 = e \times e = e$ for a double binary operation $(+, \times) \in O(\tilde{R})$. We define the *directed sum* \tilde{I} of two ideal subspaces \tilde{I}_1 and \tilde{I}_2 as follows:

- (i) $\tilde{I} = \tilde{I}_1 \cup \tilde{I}_2$;
- (ii) $\tilde{I}_1 \cap \tilde{I}_2 = \{0_+\}$, or $\tilde{I}_1 \cap \tilde{I}_2 = \emptyset$, where 0_+ denotes an unit element under the operation $+$.

Denote the directed sum of \tilde{I}_1 and \tilde{I}_2 by

$$\tilde{I} = \tilde{I}_1 \oplus \tilde{I}_2.$$

If for any $\tilde{I}_1, \tilde{I}_2, \tilde{I} = \tilde{I}_1 \oplus \tilde{I}_2$ implies that $\tilde{I}_1 = \tilde{I}$ or $\tilde{I}_2 = \tilde{I}$, then \tilde{I} is called *non-reducible*. We have the following result for the Artin multi-ring space similar to a well-known result for the Artin ring (see [12]).

Theorem 2.5 Any Artin multi-ring space $\tilde{R} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$ with double binary operation set $O(\tilde{R}) = \{(+_i, \times_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ is a directed sum of finite non-reducible ideal subspaces, and if for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, $(R_i; +_i, \times_i)$ has unit 1_{\times_i} , then

$$\tilde{R} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^m \left(\bigoplus_{j=1}^{s_i} (R_i \times_i e_{ij}) \bigcup (e_{ij} \times_i R_i) \right),$$

where $e_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq s_i$ are orthogonal idempotent elements of the ring R_i .

Proof Denote by \tilde{M} the set of ideal subspaces which can not be represented by a directed sum of finite ideal subspaces in \tilde{R} . According to Theorem 3.11, there is a minimal ideal subspace \tilde{I}_0 in \tilde{M} . It is obvious that \tilde{I}_0 is reducible.

Assume that $\tilde{I}_0 = \tilde{I}_1 + \tilde{I}_2$. Then $\tilde{I}_1 \notin \tilde{M}$ and $\tilde{I}_2 \notin \tilde{M}$. Therefore, \tilde{I}_1 and \tilde{I}_2 can be represented by directed sums of finite ideal subspaces. Whence, \tilde{I}_0 can be also represented by a directed sum of finite ideal subspaces. Contradicts that $\tilde{I}_0 \in \tilde{M}$.

Now let

$$\tilde{R} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s \tilde{I}_i,$$

where each $\tilde{I}_i, 1 \leq i \leq s$, is non-reducible. Notice that for a double operation $(+, \times)$, each non-reducible ideal subspace of \tilde{R} has the form

$$(e \times R(\times)) \bigcup (R(\times) \times e), \quad e \in R(\times).$$

Whence, we know that there is a set $T \subset \tilde{R}$ such that

$$\tilde{R} = \bigoplus_{e \in T, \times \in O(\tilde{R})} (e \times R(\times)) \bigcup (R(\times) \times e).$$

For any operation $\times \in O(\tilde{R})$ and the unit 1_{\times} , assume that

$$1_{\times} = e_1 \oplus e_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus e_l, \quad e_i \in T, \quad 1 \leq i \leq s.$$

Then

$$e_i \times 1_{\times} = (e_i \times e_1) \oplus (e_i \times e_2) \oplus \cdots \oplus (e_i \times e_l).$$

Therefore, we get that

$$e_i = e_i \times e_i = e_i^2 \quad \text{and} \quad e_i \times e_j = 0_i \quad \text{for} \quad i \neq j.$$

That is, $e_i, 1 \leq i \leq l$, are orthogonal idempotent elements of $\tilde{R}(\times)$. Notice that $\tilde{R}(\times) = R_h$ for some integer h . We know that $e_i, 1 \leq i \leq l$ are orthogonal idempotent elements of the ring $(R_h, +_h, \times_h)$. Denoted by e_{hj} for $e_j, 1 \leq j \leq l$. Consider all units in \tilde{R} , we get that

$$\tilde{R} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^m \left(\bigoplus_{j=1}^{s_i} (R_i \times_i e_{ij}) \cup (e_{ij} \times_i R_i) \right).$$

This completes the proof. \spadesuit

Corollary 2.2([12]) *Any Artin ring $(R ; +, \times)$ is a directed sum of finite ideals, and if $(R ; +, \times)$ has unit 1_\times , then*

$$R = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s R_i e_i,$$

where $e_i, 1 \leq i \leq s$ are orthogonal idempotent elements of the ring $(R; +, \times)$.

3. Open problems for a multi-ring space

Similar to Artin multi-ring space, we can also define *Noether multi-ring spaces, simple multi-ring spaces, half-simple multi-ring spaces, \dots , etc.* The open problems for these new algebraic structure are as follows.

Problem 3.1 Call a ring R a Noether ring if its every ideal chain only has finite terms. Similarly, for a multi-ring space \tilde{R} , if its every ideal multi-ring subspace chain only has finite terms, it is called a Noether multi-ring space. *Whether can we find its structures similar to Corollary 2.2 and Theorem 2.5?*

Problem 3.2 *Similar to ring theory, define a Jacobson or Brown-McCoy radical for multi-ring spaces and determine their contribution to multi-ring spaces.*

References

- [1] G.Birkhoff and S.Mac Lane, *A Survey of Modern Algebra*, Macmillan Publishing Co., Inc, 1977.
- [2] Daniel Deleanu, *A Dictionary of Smarandache Mathematics*, Buxton University Press, London & New York,2004.
- [3] L.F.Mao, On Algebraic Multi-Group Spaces, *eprint arXiv: math/0510427*, 10/2005.
- [4] L.F.Mao, *Automorphism Groups of Maps, Surfaces and Smarandache Geometries*, American Research Press, 2005.
- [5] L.Z. Nie and S.S Ding, *Introduction to Algebra*, Higher Education Publishing Press, 1994.
- [6] F.Smarandache, Mixed noneuclidean geometries, *eprint arXiv: math/0010119*, 10/2000.
- [7] F.Smarandache, *A Unifying Field in Logics. Neutrosopy: Neturosopic Probability, Set, and Logic*, American research Press, Rehoboth, 1999.

- [8] F.Smarandache, Neutrosophy, a new Branch of Philosophy, *Multi-Valued Logic*, Vol.8, No.3(2002)(special issue on Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic Logic), 297-384.
- [9] F.Smarandache, A Unifying Field in Logic: Neutrosophic Field, *Multi-Valued Logic*, Vol.8, No.3(2002)(special issue on Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic Logic), 385-438.
- [10] W.B.Vasanth Kandasamy, *Bialgebraic structures and Smarandache bialgebraic structures*, American Research Press, 2003.
- [11] W.B.Vasanth Kandasamy and F.Smarandache, *Basic Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures and Their Applications to Fuzzy and Neutrosophic Models*, HEXIS, Church Rock, 2004.
- [12] Quanyan Xong, *Ring Theory*, Wuhan University Press, 1993.